

17th International Conference on Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies, GHGT-17

20th -24th October 2024 Calgary, Canada

Regulatory and political readiness of Southern Europe for industrial implementation of CCUS technology: a case study from Italy and Greece

Alla Shogenova^{a,b*}, Kazbulat Shogenov^{a,b}, Martina Fantini^c, Katia Ferrari^d, Elisa Guasti^d, Francesco Martinelli^d, Alberto Sogni^d, Konstantinos Patlitzianas^e, Markos Damasiotis^e, Elisabeth Duetschke^f, Anne Kantel^f, Hannah Janssen^f

^aSHOGenery NGO, Pae 17a-27, Tallinn, 11414, Estonia

^bTallinn University of Technology, Department of Geology, Ehitajate tee 5, Tallinn 19086, Estonia

^cEU CORE Consulting, Piazza Castello 139, 10121 Torino, Italy

^dClust-ER Greentech Energia e Sviluppo Sostenibile, via Gobetti, 101.40133 Bologna, Italy

^eCentre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving, 19 km. Marathonos Avenue, 19009 Pikermi Attikis, Greece

^fFraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research, Breslauer Str. 48, 76139 Karlsruhe, Germany

Abstract

The Horizon Europe project HERCCULES aims to demonstrate the full CCUS value chain including the cement and waste-to-energy industry in Italy and Greece. The objective of this study is an in-depth analysis of strategies and CCUS regulations influencing the implementation of CCUS clusters in the targeted regions of the project.

The European Climate Law targets to reduce GHGE by 55% by 2030, compared to 1990, and to reach climate neutrality by 2050. Italy is one of the largest CO₂ emitters (3rd place in 2023) in EU countries. Italy and Greece have good prospects for industrial implementation of CCUS technology and becoming climate-neutral by 2050. In both countries total CO₂ emissions and emissions per capita significantly decreased by 2023 compared to 1990 and 2005. Italy has ratified the London Protocol (LP) and intends to deposit a formal declaration of provisional application of its 2009 amendment to Article 6 and to enter into discussions with France and Greece about bilateral agreements on transboundary transport of CO₂ to develop storage under the seabed. Greece is a member of the London Convention. Both countries are members of the Barcelona Convention for the Protection of the Mediterranean Sea Against Pollution, while now CO₂ injection offshore is not prohibited. CO₂ storage is not banned in Italy except for high-risk seismic areas and in Greece except for areas where the storage complex extends beyond Greek territory. However, permitting process is regulated now in Italy only for offshore depleted reservoirs.

In both countries, the first storage site (Ravenna in Italy and Prinos in Greece) is planned in depleted hydrocarbon fields which are under development now. Both storage sites are included in the 6th list of EU PCI & PMI projects for infrastructure development and cross-border cooperation. ENI already has a permit for the experimental programme “CCS Ravenna Phase 1” in Italy, while Energean has finalised the exploration of the Prinos site in Greece under the exploration permit and is waiting for a storage permit submitted in the summer of 2024. Governmental financial

* Corresponding author. Tel.: +372 566-44-668, E-mail address: alla.shogenova@taltech.ee

support is yet under discussion in Italy, but Prinos PCI has been already awarded by €150 M funding by the Greek government.

Keywords: CO₂ emissions reduction; climate strategies; CCS regulations; London Protocol; EU CCS Directive; CO₂ storage permit

1. Introduction

The Horizon Europe project HERCCULES aims to demonstrate the full CCUS value chain, including the cement and waste-to-energy industry in Italy and Greece, paving the way of CCUS technologies for Southern Europe. The objective of this study is to make an in-depth analysis of the international and national CCUS regulations influencing the development of CCUS clusters and hubs in the targeted regions of the project, focusing on energy and climate strategies for implementing the CCUS technology at European, national, and regional levels. The aim is to assess current policies and regulations, and potential disparities and identify areas of future regulatory activities.

Nomenclature

BC	Barcelona Convention
CCUS	CO ₂ capture, utilization and storage
ECL	European Climate Law
IMO	International Maritime Organisation
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
NDC	Nationally determined contribution
GHGE	Greenhouse gas emissions
Mt/y	Million tons per year
PCI	European Project of Common Interest
PMI	European Project of Mutual Interest
LP	London Protocol

2. Methods

This study is built on desk research on energy and climate strategies, related political instruments, and (policy) initiatives and actors. It is based on previous research conducted in the European finalized and ongoing projects, national reports to the European Commission (EC), and other recent policy and public documents, including National Energy and Climate Plans by 2021–2030 reported by Italy and Greece to EC in 2023–2024. Additionally, qualitative questionnaires with national and regional policymakers from ministries and agencies in Italy and Greece responsible for national policies, issuing permits for storage sites and funding agencies were conducted to identify regulatory gaps and areas for future regulatory activities. In total six Italian and two Greek policymakers answered the questionnaires [1].

3. Climate strategies and policies

3.1. Paris Climate Agreement

The UNFCCC Secretariat is the United Nations body in charge of supporting the global response against the threat of climate change. 198 countries are members of the UNFCCC.

The 2015 Paris Climate Agreement was a breakthrough in the development of the climate change mitigation program. It has very strong targets - to limit the global temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and to hold the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels. Almost all nations

participated in the agreement at the time asking to reduce CO₂ emissions significantly by 2030 and drastically by 2050. The Paris Agreement requires every nation (whether developed or developing), to take part in saving our environment. This made 196 countries endorse the document right from the beginning. At present 195 countries ratified the treaty, and 3 countries (members of UNFCCC) signed, but did not ratify (Iran, Libya, and Yemen), the latter of which are responsible for 1.38% of the world's CO₂ emissions [2].

Implementation of the Paris Agreement requires in-depth economic and social transformation, based on the best available science. The Paris Agreement works on a five-year cycle of increasingly ambitious climate action, ratcheting up - carried out by countries. Since 2020, countries have been submitting their national climate action plans to the UNFCCC secretariat, known as nationally determined contributions (NDCs). Each successive NDC must reflect an increasingly higher degree of ambition compared to the previous version [3].

3.2. European and national strategies

The European Climate Law (ECL) entered into force in July 2021. The ECL includes the European Green Deal's target to make the economy and society in Europe climate-neutral by 2050 [4]. It also includes an interim target to reduce net GHGE by at least 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 GHGE. Reaching climate neutrality by 2050 is interpreted by the EC as net zero GHGE in EU countries. This target could be achieved by reducing GHGE, financially supporting green technologies and environmental protection. The law aims to implement the goals of EU national policies to include all economic sectors and society to play an active role.

Greece adopted its National Climate Law for the first time in 2022, which includes climatic targets corresponding to the ECL to reduce GHGE by 55% by 2030 and by 80% by 2040 (compared to 1990 levels) and to achieve climate neutrality (i.e. zero total GHGE) by 2050. Greece plans to capture 3.7 Mt/y CO₂ annually from industrial processes and 5.4 Mt/y from pellet steam (bio-CO₂ to be used) and geologically store 5.4 Mt/y by 2050 [5].

Italy published the Italian Long-Term Strategy for the reduction of GHGE in January 2021, in which possible pathways to achieve climate neutrality in Italy by 2050 are described. Italy plans to reach climate neutrality by 2050 and to reduce 20–40 Mt/y of CO₂ using CCS for the hard-to-abate industry sectors. Italy defined and submitted to the EC its 2030 targets in the final National Energy and Climate Plan by 2021–2030 in the summer of 2024 [6].

3.3. National, European and world CO₂ emissions

In 2023 the EU27 were among the six largest GHG emitters in the world (including China, the United States, India, Russia and Brazil). In 2023, all EU27 countries except Croatia and Cyprus decreased their total emissions compared to 2022 (Table 1). Among the EU27 countries Germany remained the largest GHG emitter in 2023, followed by France, Italy, Poland and Spain. Italy moved from the 4th place in 2022 to the 3rd place in 2023.

In the EU in 2023, GHG emissions decreased in all sectors compared to 2022. The largest decrease was in the power industry sector, where emissions decreased by 20.1%. The emissions in industrial combustion and processes decreased by 8.1% in 2023 compared to 2022.

Table 1. CO₂ total emissions in Mt [7], [8]

Country	1990	2000	2005	2015	2020	2022	2023
Italy, San Marino and the Holy See	426.42	454.72	493.49	354.02	295.87	332.77	305.49
Greece	77.90	96.05	103.62	69.45	52.37	54.93	51.67
EU27	3809.70	3563.26	3689.08	3086.21	2641.19	2756.91	2512.07
Global Total	22680.40	25725.44	30044.54	36300.47	36154.31	38246.62	39023.94

CO₂ emissions per capita significantly decreased in EU27 countries in 2023 compared with 1990 and 2005, including Italy and Greece. In both countries, CO₂ emissions per capita (5.19 t in Italy) and (4.69 t in Greece) are

lower than the EU27 average (5.66 t) but Italian emissions are still higher than the Global Total Average (4.86 t) (Table 2).

Table 2. CO₂ emissions per capita in tons [7], [8]

Country	1990	2000	2005	2010	2015	2020	2022	2023
Italy, San Marino and the Holy See	7.46	7.94	8.39	7.10	5.95	5.00	5.65	5.19
Greece	7.60	8.62	9.17	7.78	6.19	4.72	4.97	4.69
EU27	9.07	8.32	8.48	7.75	6.98	5.95	6.21	5.66
Global Total	4.26	4.19	4.59	4.89	4.92	4.64	4.81	4.86

4. CCS Regulations

4.1. International and Regional

At the international level, the most important regulations affecting CCS are the international conventions dealing with the transboundary shipments of CO₂. These include the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean (Barcelona Convention), the Protocol to the Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter (London Protocol), and the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (known as the OSPAR Convention). Italy and Greece are among the 21 Parties to the Barcelona Convention, and members of the London Convention, however, only Italy has also ratified the London Protocol (LP). Italy and Greece are parties of the OSPAR Convention under the European Union sign.

An amendment was adopted in 2009 to address the potential incompatibility between Article 6 of the LP and CCS activities. The former Article 6 prohibits the “export of wastes or other matter to other countries for dumping or incineration at sea”, while the 2009 amendments Article 6 (LP.3(4)) enable - exclusively - the export of carbon dioxide streams for sequestration in transboundary sub-seabed geological formations. However, this amendment has not yet entered into force as only 10 countries have adopted it by December 2023: Norway and the UK in 2011, The Netherlands in 2014, Iran in 2016, Finland in 2017, Estonia in 2019, Sweden in 2020, Denmark, Belgium and the Republic of Korea in 2022, and Switzerland and Australia in 2024 [9]. However, the amendment to the LP requires acceptance by two-thirds of the Parties to enter into force.

The 14th Meeting of the Contracting Parties to the LP decided on October 11, 2019, to allow for the provisional application of the 2009 amendment pending its entry into force by those Contracting Parties which have deposited a declaration to this effect.

Until now, only nine countries sent declarations to the Secretary-General of IMO on their provisional applications of the 2009 amendment, pending entry into force. Norway and The Netherlands sent their declarations in 2020, while Denmark, the Republic of Korea, the UK, Belgium and Sweden in 2022, while Switzerland and Australia sent their declarations to IMO in 2024 [9].

Italy is planning to deposit a formal declaration of provisional application of the 2009 amendment to Article 6 of the LP and to enter discussions with France and Greece to conclude bilateral agreements on transboundary transport of CO₂ to develop projects for permanent geological storage under the seabed [6].

The Barcelona Convention (BC) – is the Convention for the Protection of the Mediterranean Sea Against Pollution. It was adopted on 16 February 1976 in Barcelona, entered into force in 1978, and was amended in 1995, when it was renamed to the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean. The amendments to the BC entered into force in 2004. The BC and its seven Protocols adopted in the framework of the Mediterranean Action Plan (MAP) constitute the principal regional legally binding Multilateral Environmental Agreement (MEA) in the Mediterranean UNEP/MAP and the Contracting Parties to the BC are 21 Mediterranean countries and the EU. The amendments adopted in 1995 have yet to be ratified by Bosnia and Herzegovina [10]

4.2. EU CCS Directive and its implementation

Directive 2009/31/EC of the European Parliament and the Council on the geological storage of carbon dioxide (Carbon Capture and Storage Directive – “CCS Directive”) establishes a legal framework for the environmentally safe geological storage of CO₂. The CCS Directive aims to ensure that there is no significant risk of leakage of CO₂ or damage to health or the environment and to prevent any adverse effects on the security of the transport network or storage sites [11].

To implement Directive 2009/31/EC, Italy passed a new legislation to regulate the geological storage of carbon dioxide. Legislative Decree No 162 of 14 September 2011 entered into force on 5 October 2011 [12]. CO₂ storage is permitted in Italy both onshore and offshore except for the country’s seismic areas. Exploration and storage permits are always required.

In December 2023, Italy published a Legislative Decree n.181, namely “Urgent provisions for the country's energy security, the promotion of the use of renewable energy sources, support for energy-intensive businesses and for reconstruction in the territories affected by the exceptional flood events that occurred starting from 1 May 2023” (GU General Series n.287 of 09-12-2023) which entered into force on 10/12/2023 [13]. Part 7 of this decree amended the Legislative Decree No 162 of 14 September 2011, which previously regulated CO₂ storage in suitable geological formations, including experimental programmes. The amendments, including additional clarification and some editions, were made to requests for obtaining exploration licences, applications for authorisation to carry out experimental programmes of geological storage of CO₂ and applications for CO₂ authorisations of CO₂ geological storage submitted after the date of entry into force of this Decree. Experimental programmes for the geological storage of CO₂ is defined as “a geological storage of CO₂ that takes place, over a period limited and for experimental purposes, in deposits of spent hydrocarbons located in the territorial sea and within the exclusive economic zone and the continental shelf”, while authorisations for the carrying out experimental programmes for the geological storage of CO₂ shall be issued to applicants, on the advice of the Committee, by the Ministry of Environment and Energy Security. During the period of validity of the authorizations, no incompatible uses of the site under investigation are allowed by the provisions of the authorisation itself [13].

Finally, regulations were added: „For the case of more than one storage site in the same hydraulic unit, the potential pressure interactions must be such that all sites simultaneously comply with the provisions of this Decree” [13].

In Greece, the Ministerial Decision [14], as amended, transposed the CCS Directive 2009/31/EC into Greek law. The decision largely follows the principles of the EU CCS Directive. Industrial CO₂ storage is permitted both onshore and offshore, except for areas where the storage complex extends beyond Greek territory. Exploration and storage permits are always required.

The recent law L.4920/2022 (art.228 par.1), as amended by L.4964/2022 (Article 175), designates the Hellenic Hydrocarbons and Energy Resources Management Company (HEREMA) as the competent authority for the licensing, monitoring and supervision of carbon dioxide storage projects. Moreover, Article 173 of L.4964/2022 introduces a new licensing process for CO₂ exploration and storage permits for economical operators who already hold hydrocarbon exploration and production rights in areas which could potentially be used for carbon dioxide storage [15].

4.3. Assessing storage capacity and application for exploration and storage permits

Italy plans to start CO₂ storage in depleted gas fields offshore Ravenna (Fig. 1a) in the Adriatic Sea (potential of 515 Mt CO₂). Potential onshore storage capacity of 69 Mt in the Ravenna area and 35 Mt in Sicily are also reported in the Italian plan [6].

ENI S.p.A. was granted the first authorisation in Italy to carry out an experimental programme (called CCS Ravenna Phase 1) for the capture, transport and geological storage of CO₂ from the ENI power plant in Casalborsetti (Ravenna), in the storage complex in an offshore natural gas production area. The implementation of the Ravenna project will be a first step in replicating similar initiatives in the other depleted fields.

The project in Ravenna is part of the Callisto PCI & PMI (Project of Common and Mutual Interest) [16]. It will inject 25 Kt/y CO₂ from the ENI natural gas plant in Casalborsetti in Phase 1 (2024) and will reach 4 Mt/y storage capacity in Phase 2 during 2027-2030, with a potential expansion of up to 16 Mt/y after 2030 according to market demand. CO₂ will be injected into the depleted gas field at about 3 km depth. CO₂ emissions from hard-to-abate industry, waste-to-energy and natural gas power plants will be transported to the storage sites by pipelines and by ships.

CO₂ will be captured in Italy mainly from the hard-to-abate industry, which produced 67.5 Mt CO₂ in 2022. Bio-CO₂ could be captured from waste-to-energy plants for use and storage. In 2022 there were 36 waste-to-energy plants in Italy which produced 7.5 Mt of Bio-CO₂.

As it was reported on the 3rd of September 2024, HERCCULES partners ENI and SNAM started in August operations in Ravenna CCS, Italy's first Carbon Capture and Storage project [17].

Greece is still in the process of identifying the areas from which storage sites may be selected following Article 4(1) of the EU CCS directive. Although a preliminary assessment of potential storage areas has been conducted, this has only been done on a qualitative basis and no specific areas have been officially designated yet. However, the Prinos Basin, which includes the almost depleted offshore Prinos oil field (NE Greece), is currently a mature candidate site for carbon storage in Greece, for which an exploration permit of 22-month duration was issued by HEREMA to Energean in September 2022, following the permitting process of L. 4964/2022. The permit was granted to explore the potential for CO₂ storage at the Prinos complex (Fig. 1b), where it currently holds the oil & gas exploration and production rights [18].

Figure 1. (a) Ravenna storage site in Italy [17]; (b) Prinos storage site in Greece [18]

Two other projects in Greece have already been selected for co-financing by the Innovation Fund: an IRIS project for CO₂ capture at the H₂ production plant of a refinery in Corinth, and an IFESTOS project for CO₂ capture in a cement plant in Viotia.

Energean Oil&Gas Company studied the Prinos field together with Halliburton Company. Exploration results show that one Mt CO₂ can be injected annually into the Prinos field in the first phase, with injections planned to start by the end of 2025. The second stage will start in 2027 with an injection of 3 Mt/y CO₂ from the hard-to-abate industry in SE Europe. ENERGEAN submitted a CO₂ storage License application for the Prinos storage site in June 2024. Prinos PCI for offshore storage at Prinos field from Greece by pipeline and from Bulgaria, Hungary, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, and Slovenia by ship is included in the 6th list of European PCI&PMIs [16]. Within Prinos PCI&PMI, eight non-binding MoUs with industrial companies (from Greece, Croatia, Southern Italy, and Bulgaria) for 4.8 Mt/y CO₂ are signed by ENERGEAN. Greek Government committed financial support of 150 MEuro from the European Recovery and Resilience Facility [18].

5. Country profiles

5.1. Italy

Italy has ratified the Paris Climate Agreement on 11 Nov 2016. Its total fossil CO₂ emissions decreased from 423.3 Mt in 1990 to 305.49 Mt in 2023. CO₂ emissions per capita in Italy decreased from 8.39 t in 2005 (maximum since 1990) to 5.19 t in 2022 (Table 2). Italy plans to reach climate neutrality by 2050. Based on the objectives set by the Italian Long-Term Strategy, the target for reducing greenhouse gas emissions is expected to be approximately 20 to 40 Mt/y CO₂ by 2050 by storing CO₂, compared with emissions of around 50–60 Mt/year in 2019 from hard-to-abate sectors. Italy defined and submitted to EC its 2030 targets in the Final National Energy and Climate Plan in 2024, where CCS plans for CO₂ storage in the Ravenna hub in the Adriatic Sea are explained in detail, including CO₂ transport options by ships and pipelines from the Italian emission clusters and possibility to provide large-scale open access infrastructure to industrial plants from Southern Europe. For the cross-border CCS cooperation Mediterranean CCS Plan was drawn up by Italy, France and Greece to support the application of the Callisto Mediterranean CO₂ Network, Prinos CO₂ storage and Augusta CO₂ projects [6].

Italy has ratified the London Protocol but has not ratified yet the 2009 amendment to Article 6, enabling the export of carbon dioxide streams for sequestration in transboundary sub-seabed geological formations. Italy intends to deposit a formal declaration of provisional application of the 2009 amendment to Article 6 of the London Protocol and to enter discussions with France and Greece to conclude bilateral agreements on transboundary transport of CO₂ to develop projects for permanent geological storage under the seabed [6].

Italy is a member of the Barcelona Convention for the Protection of the Mediterranean Sea Against Pollution. Its Protocol, amended in 1995, prohibits all dumping activities with some exceptions, where CO₂ is not yet included. However, the 1995 amendment is not yet in force, and by this time CO₂ injection offshore is not prohibited [10].

Italy passed a new legislation to regulate the geological storage of carbon dioxide. Legislative Decree No 162 of 14 September 2011 entered into force on 5 October 2011. CO₂ storage is permitted in Italy except for the seismic areas.

The regulatory framework is being updated to speed up the authorisation process and to define the technical rules and requirements for the transport and storage of CO₂, as well as the business model and the associated regulatory framework for CCS.

The INECP 2019 recognised the possibility of capturing and storing carbon in both the energy and industrial sectors by 2040 to achieve full decarbonisation of the energy system by 2050. Carbon capture, transport and storage facilities were subsequently explicitly included in the list of infrastructure needed to achieve the INECP objectives (Decree-Law 76/2020 and Decree-Law 77/2021). As such, they are of overriding public interest and eligible for a dedicated accelerated authorisation process. Italy intended to fill any remaining regulatory or procedural gaps in the process of permitting storage and development of the CCS sector. This is partially done by the recently implemented Legislative Decree n.181 [13].

Italy has very good geological options for geological storage of CO₂ emissions in the depleted gas fields and saline aquifers both onshore and offshore. In the EU GeoCapacity project CO₂ storage capacity in deep saline aquifers was estimated as 4669 Mt and in hydrocarbon fields as 1810 Mt [19]. Monitoring requirements of the storage sites in Italian regulations mostly correspond to the EU CCS Directive. Italian CCS Decree includes Annex I (analogue to Annex I to CCS directive about characterisation and assessment of the potential storage complex) and Annex II (criteria for establishing and updating the plan) analogue to the Annex II to CCS directive.

An analysis of the storage potential was launched in Italy focusing on depleted oil & gas fields. The results of ENI's analyses showed a storage potential for the oil & gas fields used in Italy of around 750 Mt [6].

Italian CCS Decree in Article 28 obliges operators of CO₂ transport networks and storage sites to guarantee the connection and free access to its transportation network and storage sites to other operators in a transparent and non-discriminatory manner. However, it is also stated that “transport network operators and operators of storage sites may refuse access for lack of ability or link”. Article 30 of the Italian CCS Decree regulates transnational cooperation on CO₂ storage and requires the Ministry of Economic Development and Environment to comply with the Decree and

Community standards while promoting the conclusion of agreements with non-EU countries. Business models, access rights, regulation and network codes are under discussion in the Italian ministerial working groups and will be updated in the short terms.

EU ETS Operates in Italy, as an EU Member State. Italy has not introduced a national Carbon Tax yet.

Italy granted ENI S.p.A. the first license for an experimental programme called CCS Ravenna Phase 1. It will inject 25 Kt/y CO₂ from the ENI natural gas plant in Casalborgorsetti in Phase 1 (2024) into the depleted gas field at about 3 km depth and will reach 4 Mt/y storage capacity as a part of Callisto PCI in Phase 2 during 2027-2030, with a potential expansion up to 16 Mt/y after 2030. Industrial CO₂ emissions will be transported by onshore pipelines and ships.

5.2. Greece

Greece has ratified the Paris Climate Agreement on 14 Oct 2016. In Greece, total fossil CO₂ emissions decreased from 77.9 Mt in 1990 to 51.67 Mt in 2023. CO₂ emissions per capita in Greece decreased from 9.17 t in 2005 (maximum since 1990) to 4.69 t in 2023 (Table 2). The largest CO₂ in Greece are power plants, refineries, and cement plants.

According to EU NDC submitted in October 2023 and Regulation (EU) 2023/857 sets an EU-level greenhouse gas emission reduction target of 40% by 2030, compared to 2005, for the sectors that it covers. Greece has a greenhouse gas emission reduction target of 22.7% by 2030, compared to 2005.

Greece plans to capture annually 3.7 Mt/y CO₂ from industrial processes and 5.4 Mt/y from pellet steam (bio-CO₂ to be used) and store geologically 5.4 Mt/y by 2050 [5].

Table 3. CCUS targets reported by Greece Draft National Energy and Climate Plan by 2021–2030 [5]

Planned annual volumes, Mt/y	2035	2040	2045	2050
CO ₂ captured from pellet steam (Bio-CO ₂)	0.066	2.474	3.203	5.379
CO ₂ captured from conductor electrode	0	1.077	1.13	1.743
CO ₂ captured from industrial processes	0.932	3.287	3.447	3.653
CO ₂ storage capacity available		4.363	4.577	5.395

Greece is a member of the London Convention but has not yet ratified the London Protocol and did not report on plans to do it. Greece is a member of the Barcelona Convention for the Protection of the Mediterranean Sea Against Pollution. Its Protocol, amended in 1995, prohibits all dumping activities with some exceptions, where CO₂ is not yet included. However, the 1995 amendment is not yet in force, and by now CO₂ injection offshore is not prohibited.

In Greece, the Ministerial Decision 48416/2037/E.103/2011 [14], as amended, transposed the CCS Directive 2009/31/EC into Greek law. The decision largely follows the philosophy of the EU CCS Directive.

The recent law L.4920/2022 (art.228 par.1), as amended by L.4964/2022 (Article 175), designates the Hellenic Hydrocarbons and Energy Resources Management Company (HEREMA) as the competent authority for the licensing, monitoring, and supervision of carbon storage projects. Moreover, Article 173 of L.4964/2022 introduces a new licensing process for CO₂ exploration and storage permits for economic operators who already hold hydrocarbon exploration and production rights in areas that could be used for carbon storage [5].

Greece has very good geological options for the storage of CO₂ emissions. In the EUGeoCapacity project, different potential sites for CO₂ storage in Greece with total storage capacity in deep saline aquifers and hydrocarbon fields of 2190 Mt were reported. The total effective storage capacity in aquifers alone in Greece was estimated to be around 184 Mt [19]. This CO₂ storage capacity concerns the Tertiary sedimentary basins of Prinos, West Thessaloniki, and a part of the Mesohellenic Trough [20]. CO₂ storage capacity in the Miocene Pentalofofos formation was estimated recently as 1435 Gt CO₂ [21].

An exploration permit of a 22-month duration was granted by HEREMA to Energean in September 2022 to explore the potential for CO₂ storage at the Prinos complex, where it currently holds the oil & gas exploration and production rights [5]. Exploration results show that one Mt CO₂ can be injected annually into the Prinos field in the first phase with injections planned to start by the end of 2025. The second stage will start in 2027 with an injection of 3 Mt/y

CO₂ from the hard-to-abate industry in SE Europe. Energean submitted a CO₂ storage License application for the Prinos storage site in June 2024. Prinos PCI for offshore storage at Prinos field from Greece by pipeline, and from Bulgaria, Hungary, Cyprus, Greece, Italy and Slovenia by ship, is included in the 6th list of European PCIs. 11 non-binding MoUs with industrial companies (from Greece, Croatia, Southern Italy, and Bulgaria) for 5.44 Mt/y CO₂ signed by Energean are supporting for future cross-border development of the Prinos full value chain CCUS project. Awarded governmental financial support of €150 M from the European Recovery and Resilience Facility is additional advantage for the Prinos project development in Greece.

6. Questionnaire on CCUS for policymakers

In the framework of the HERCCULES project, a qualitative questionnaire was prepared to investigate national policymakers' approach concerning the international and national CCUS regulations influencing the implementation of CCUS cluster projects and hubs in targeted regions (London Protocol, EU CCS Directive, EU ETS Directive, etc.), as well as the regulatory situation and the political strategies for implementing integrated-chain CCUS at European, national and regional level [1].

6.1. Italy

Among the six Italian policymakers that responded to the questionnaire, most (5 versus 1) positively answered the question about their expectations to implement CCUS in Italy on a wider industrial scale by 2050 (Fig. 2a). The answers were not uniform about governmental activities to support CCUS cluster and hub projects (Fig. 2b). Policymakers underlined 1) recently increased interest partly due to the ENI's industrial project, 2) the need of CCUS technologies to reduce GHG emissions by industry and 3) collaboration of Italy with other Mediterranean countries for CO₂ storage. Among the negative aspects, the low funding for CCUS technologies and lack of funds for applied research for different industries and infrastructure were mentioned. Also assigning „experimental” status to the Ravenna project instead of adopting established techniques in northern Europe, was criticized.

Fig. 2. (a) Answers of Italian policymakers to the question: Do you expect that CCUS will be implemented in Italy on a wider industrial scale by 2050? (b) Answers of Italian policymakers to the question: Does your government actively work on supporting CCUS cluster and hub projects in Italy? [1]

Awareness of Italian policymakers about international CCS regulations, including Article 6 of the London Protocol, and Italian plans to implement it, was not uniform (three options selected equally).

Most of the Italian policymakers answered positively about gaps in the national CCS regulations. They explained that currently CO₂ storage is permitted in Italy, only for depleted gas fields. The need for more clear monitoring and

permitting regulations was also mentioned. The absent decree required under Article 7 to identify the areas of the national territory and the exclusive economic zone within which storage sites may be selected under this decree and the areas in which storage is not permitted, is mentioned. The new regulation DL181/2023 with one sentence about issuance of licenses for experimental programs in depleted hydrocarbon reservoirs located in the territorial sea was also mentioned.

Answering economic questions including EU ETS and national carbon tax, most of the policymakers positively agreed that a national CO₂ tax could be or maybe introduced in Italy to support national CCUS projects.

Answering questions about developing new and reusing old infrastructure, the policymakers mentioned the project in Ravenna where some infrastructure will be reused and a recent study [22] where the ability of Italy to achieve neutrality goals, while creating added value, was reported.

6.2. Greece

As only two policymakers answered, the data for Greece is statistically less representative, and we will describe their answers in shorter terms than for Italy.

Both Greek politicians answered that CCUS technology is low or not a priority in the Greek climate agenda. However, one policymaker answered positively, and another was not sure about CCUS implementation in Greece on a wider industrial scale by 2050. Their awareness and activities related to the London Protocol and cross-border export and import of CO₂ were low.

The policymakers answered that only one exploration permit for the Prinios site is given and there are probably gaps in secondary legislation, such as storage fees and how the state will also derive revenue from the concession of storage space. About financial support to CCUS projects in Greece, both answered „No, but it is on the agenda“.

About using CO₂ taxes for CCUS projects and introducing a national CO₂ tax both policymakers answered „maybe“.

They answered „yes“ and „maybe“ about current regulations allowing to give permits for CCUS to the oil and gas license owners, but were not aware of national plans for CO₂ pipeline infrastructure to be built.

7. Conclusions

- Italy and Greece have made ambitious plans for climate mitigation, and the development of a wider industrial implementation of CCUS technology is ongoing. In both countries total CO₂ emissions and emissions per capita significantly decreased by 2023 compared to 1990 and 2005.
- In the NECP 2023 Greece reported to the EC ambitious climate targets, which are mostly in line with EC plans, or even higher. Italy submitted its final NECP by 2021-2030 in 2024 with significantly increased details for its CCUS plans by 2030 and 2050, compared to the draft version 2023.
- Both countries implemented the EU CCS Directive to the full extent that permits CO₂ geological storage and recently made some needed updates and changes. However, there are some areas where additional improvements and regulatory developments should be additionally made in Greece, such as transboundary issues and third-party access to the storage sites.
- National CO₂ storage capacity estimated in research projects and publications is high enough in both countries for domestic needs and cross-border cooperation. Italy decided to start with depleted gas fields and exploit at least 500 Mt of their capacity, while Greece's national authorities are in the phase of planning to estimate their capacity and considered three options for storage media.
- Concerning international regulations, Italy is in a more advanced situation, as it is a party to the London Protocol and planning to implement an amendment to Article 6, permitting CO₂ export for storage under the seabed. Greece is a part of the London Convention, but not of the Protocol and did not report any plans in this direction.
- Both Italy and Greece did not implement national CO₂ tax and politicians answered either positively or „maybe“ that this instrument could be helpful for CCUS development.

- Slightly more Italian policymakers participated in the questionnaire survey. It was noticed that they were better informed regarding regulatory issues and national plans than the Greek policymakers. A higher percentage of Italian politicians gave positive answers about the possibility of implementing industrial-scale CCUS and CCS-related regulations as compared to negative or uncertain answers from Greek policymakers.
- Some policymakers from both countries mentioned in their answers that CCUS is not yet a priority in their country.
- In 2023 Greece submitted a national report to the EC about EU CCS Directive updates and applications, while Italy was one of two EU countries that did not submit the report. However, in December 2023 Italy published regulation “Decreto Energia” in Gazzetta Ufficiale, composed of 21 parts, where CCS regulation was updated mostly about authorization process and experimental CO₂ storage, but not only, in the extensive part 7 of this law.
- In both countries, the first storage site (Ravenna in Italy and Prinos in Greece) is planned in depleted hydrocarbon fields which are under development now and possible governmental financial support is yet under discussion in Italy, but Prinos PCI already has been awarded €150 M funding by the Greek government.
- Both storage sites are included in the list of EU PCI & PMI for transport and storage infrastructure development, and cross-border cooperation is negotiated.
- However, ENI already has a license for CO₂ injection in Ravenna (Italy), while Energean has finalized the exploration of the Prinos site in Greece under the exploration permit and is waiting for a storage permit.

Acknowledgements

This research is funded by the European Union project HERCCULES which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101096691. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

References

- [1] Shogenova A, Shogenov K, Fantini M, Ferrari K, Guasti E, Martinelli F, Sogni A, Tzaos P, Patlitzianas K, Damasiotis M, Duetschke E, Kantel A. & Janssen H. Analysis of policy alignment including country case studies. D8.1 of HERCCULES project; 2024. 51 pp.
- [2] UNFCCC. Paris Agreement - Status of Ratification; 2024.
- [3] UNFCCC. Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs); 2024.
- [4] European Commission, European Climate Law - European Commission (europa.eu). https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/european-climate-law_en; 2023.
- [5] Hellenic Republic Ministry of Environment and Energy. National Energy and Climate Plan – Preliminary Draft Revised Version; October 2023. 307 pp.
- [6] INECP-Italy, Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security of Italy. National Integrated Plan for Energy and Climate by 2021-2030; July 2024. 490 pp.
- [7] Crippa M, Guizzardi D, Pagani F, Banja M, Muntean M, Schaaf E, Monforti-Ferrario F, Becker WE, Quadrelli R, Riskez Martin A, Taghavi-Moharamli P, Köykkä J, Grassi G, Rossi S, Melo J, Oom D, Branco A, San-Miguel J, Manca G, Pisoni E, Vignati E and Pekar F. GHG emissions of all world countries. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg; 2024. doi:10.2760/4002897, JRC138862
- [8] EDGAR-2024-GHG. <https://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/report>; 2024.
- [9] IMO. Status of IMO treaties: Comprehensive information on the status of multilateral Conventions and instruments in respect of which the International Maritime Organization or its Secretary-General performs depositary or other functions; November 2024. pp. 585-592. <https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/About/Conventions/StatusOfConventions/Status%202024.pdf>
- [10] UNEP/MAP. Mediterranean Action Plan (MAP)-Barcelona Convention; 2024. <https://www.unep.org/uneppmap/>
- [11] European Commission, Directive 2009/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the geological storage of carbon dioxide and amending Council Directive 85/337/EEC, European Parliament and Council Directives 2000/60/EC, 2001/80/EC, 2004/35/EC, 2006/12/EC, 2008/1/EC and Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006 (1). Official Journal of the European Union; 2009, L140, 114-35
- [12] Decreto Legislativo n. 162, 2011. Attuazione della Direttiva 2009/31/CE in materia di stoccaggio geologico del biossido di carbonio, nonché modifica delle direttive 85/337/CEE, 2000/60/CE, 2001/80/CE, 2004/35/CE, 2006/12/CE, 2008/1/CE e del Regolamento (CE) n. 1013/2006, 2011. Gazzetta Ufficiale della Repubblica Italiana. 231; 2011-10-04.

- [13] Decreto-Legge 9 dicembre 2023, n. 181. Disposizioni urgenti per la sicurezza energetica del Paese, la materia di ricostruzione nei territori colpiti dagli eccezionali eventi alluvionali verificatisi a partire dal 1° maggio 2023. (23G00195) (GU Serie Generale n.287 del 09-12-2023). Gazzetta Ufficiale della Repubblica Italiana, 2023-12-9, <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2023/12/09/23G00195/sg/>.
- [14] Government Gazette B' 2516, Measures and conditions for the geological storage of carbon dioxide - Amendment of No. 29457/1511/2005 (992/B) joint ministerial decision, Presidential Decree 51/2007 (54/A) and Presidential Decree 148/2009 (190/A), in compliance with the provisions of Directive 2009/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the geological storage of carbon dioxide and amending Council Directive 85/337/EEC, Directives 2000/60/EC, 2004/35/EC, 2008/1/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006. Government Gazette 2116B, 2011.
- [15] HEREMA, Member State report on Implementation of Directive 2009/31/EC on the geological storage of carbon dioxide ("CCS Directive"); 2023.
- [16] PCI-PMI transparency platform, https://ec.europa.eu/energy/infrastructure/transparency_platform/map-viewer/main.html; 2024.
- [17] ENI website. Eni and Snam launch Ravenna CCS, Italy's first Carbon Capture and Storage project; 2024, <https://www.eni.com/en-IT/media/press-release/2024/09/eni-snam-launch-ravenna-css-italy-s-first-carbon-capture-storage-project.html>
- [18] Energean PLC. Prinos CO2; 2024. <https://www.energean.com/operations/greece/prinos-co2/>
- [19] Vangkilde-Pedersen T. et al. FP6 EU GeoCapacity Project, Assessing European Capacity for Geological Storage of Carbon Dioxide, Storage Capacity. WP2, D16 report; 2009. 166 pp.
- [20] Hatziyannis G, Country updates: Greece. In: Vangkilde-Pedersen T, editor. WP2 Report –Storage capacity. EU GeoCapacity –Assessing European Capacity for Geological storage of Carbon Dioxide. Project no. SE6-518318; 2009. p. 144-147.
- [21] Koukouzas N, Gemeni V. Potential CO2 storage sites in Greece – A review. 15th International Congress of the Geological Society of Greece Athens, 22-24 May, 2019. Harokopio University of Athens, Greece Bulletin of the Geological Society of Greece. Sp. Pub. 7 Ext. Abs. GSG2019-197; 2019.
- [22] Ambrosetti. InnoTech Report 2023: l'ecosistema italiano dell'innovazione, sfide e opportunità; 2023. 283 pp. 2023 Technology Forum | The European House - Ambrosetti.